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User roles in Digitala

The user roles in Digitala follow the roles given in the Moodle environment. There are some basic differences between admin, teacher and student roles in Digitala. These differences will be demonstrated in this manual.

See figures among the text by clicking on them.

- An administrator can
 - change the address and the key of the API server
 - change the address of the feedback site popping up on the report view up on report view
- A teacher can
 - create a new Digitala activity (=assignment) on a course page
 - edit and delete the Digitala activity afterwards
 - see student results on the Digitala activity
 - suggest changes and add feedback to the automated assessment on a student evaluation report
 - download database reports from the Digitala activity.
- A student can
 - test their microphone on the begin view
 - see the assignment prompt and materials on the assignment view
 - record, listen and submit their speech performance on the assignment view
 - receive an automated evaluation of their performance on the evaluation view
 - see teacher’s feedback about the automated evaluation
 - give feedback on the Digitala plugin

Admin usage

The admin is allowed to do all the same things as a teacher and a student.

Admin can also * set the address and key to the API-server * set the feedback link for users that will be shown on the report page.

These settings can be changed in Moodle in *Site administration* -> *Plugins* -> *Digitala*.

Figure: Admin settings

The screenshot shows the Moodle admin settings for the Digitala plugin. The page title is "Digitala". There are three main settings sections:

- Address for API-server** (digitala | api): The input field contains "http://digitala-api:3000". Below it, the default is "http://digitala-api:3000". A label below the field says "Give address to the API-server."
- Key for the API-server** (digitala | key): The input field contains "digitala". Below it, the default is "digitala". A label below the field says "Give valid key for the API-server authentication".
- Give address to feedback site** (digitala | feedback): The input field is empty. Below it, the default is a redacted URL. A label below the field says "Give the address of the site where users can sen feedback on evaluation page."

At the bottom of the settings area is a blue button labeled "Save changes".

Teacher usage

A teacher is allowed to do all the same things as a student.

Teacher can also * create a new Digitala activity (= assignment) on a course page * edit and delete the Digitala activity afterwards * see student results on the Digitala activity * suggest changes and add feedback to automated assessment on a student evaluation report * download database reports from the Digitala activity.

Creating a new Digitala on a course

A teacher with editing permissions can add a Digitala activity (= assignment) on a course page by turning the editing on on a course front page and then adding a new activity called "Digitala".

<https://user-images.githubusercontent.com/6292793/166822139-507da7e6-8112-40de-905e-21ea563adc66.mp4>

Figure: Adding Digitala on course

On the adding page the teacher has the option to give the activity a **name** which will be shown on the course page. Other options include:

- **Language** - whether the assignment is for evaluating/practicing L2 Finnish or Swedish speech
- **Type** - whether the assignment is to read a given text aloud or to talk more freely about the topic of the assignment
- **Time limit** - A time limit for student's speech performance which maxes up and defaults to 5 minutes.
- **Attempt limit** - Optional limit for how many times students can submit their answer for evaluation. Defaults to unlimited.

- **Assignment** - The assignment that the user should complete. This prompt will be sent to the evaluation API in the Freeform type of assignment, so if the API is trained with these kinds of tasks, it should also give a reasonable evaluation for “Task completion”.
- **Material** - If using Read-aloud type of assignment, the text to be read should be provided here, preferably in plain text. In Read-aloud type this text will be sent to the evaluation API and the speech performance will be compared to this text. In Freeform type this field can be used to provide additional material such as guiding questions or different media snippets.
- **More information** Information provided to the student on evaluation page. Could include for example audio examples of different levels of speech performances.
- **Description** - This description won't be shown anywhere at the moment so there's no need for the use of it.

Figure: Digitala settings

Adding a new Digitala

[Expand all](#)

General

Name

Language

Type

Time limit minutes

Attempt limit

Assignment

Material

↶ A B I ≡ ≡ ≡ ≡ 🔗 🔄

😊 🖼️ 📄 🎤 🎥 📎 H-P

More information

↶ A B I ≡ ≡ ≡ ≡ 🔗 🔄

😊 🖼️ 📄 🎤 🎥 📎 H-P

Description

↶ A B I ≡ ≡ ≡ ≡ 🔗 🔄

😊 🖼️ 📄 🎤 🎥 📎 H-P

Editing and deleting a Digitala

The Digitala setup can be edited from the activity wheel inside the Digitala activity.

<https://user-images.githubusercontent.com/6292793/166821889-c483e54d-e87b-4c41-88e2-a6e2b558779a.mp4>

Figure: Editing Digitala inside the activity

Also the editing mode on the course front page allows both editing and deleting the Digitala activity.

Figure: Editing Digitala from course front page

See student results

A teacher can access the overview of the student results by choosing “View student results” on the activity wheel in the Digitala.

<https://user-images.githubusercontent.com/6292793/166822414-f16d9742-1304-404e-8a36-e39894d15a6b.mp4>

Figure: Navigating to student results overview

Here the teacher can see the proficiency or pronunciation grade of the students' speech performance, the duration of the recording, the number of tries the student has made and the status of the evaluation. Here the teacher can also delete the attempts from one or all students, which will result in resetting the student's attempts to zero. From the link "See report" the teacher can see a detailed version of the student's evaluation report.

<https://user-images.githubusercontent.com/6292793/166822489-a1c4f6a7-79a9-4e3e-b1ef-71951b53f780.mp4>

Figure: Overview of student results

User results							
Student	Pronunciation	Time	Tries	Status	Timestamp	Evaluation report	Delete all
Admin User	4.00	00:04	4	Evaluated	26.04.2022 16:40:58	See report	Delete attempt
Essi Esimerkki	4.00	00:04	1	Evaluated	24.04.2022 19:30:17	See report	Delete attempt

Export all attempts as CSV Export all feedbacks for attempts as CSV

Suggest changes or add feedback to automated assessment

On the overview of the student results the teacher can see a detailed version of the student's performance by clicking the link "See report".

Figure: Teacher view of student's evaluation report

Testikurssi 1

Dashboard / Courses / test1 / General / readaloud fin csv

Essi Esimerkki

Assignment

Material

Assignment

Language: Finnish | Type: Read aloud

Lue teksti.

Evaluation report - includes some teacher feedback

Submitted: 24.04.2022 19:30:17

This feedback concerns only the speech sample you produced and it does not cover all aspects of your oral language skills. A machine produces your grades automatically. We have taught the machine with speech from other language learners together with other language-specific data.

There is no limit set for the number of attempts on this assignment.

▶ 0:00 / 0:00 ◀ ⋮

Plain text

Show corrections

A transcript of your speech sample

mustan kissan paksut posuilit

Fluency

4/4

This measure reflects the speed, pauses, and hesitations in your speech. Based on the automatic grading, it seems that your speech is very fluent and no disturbing pauses, breaks, or hesitations occur.

Teacher's grade suggestion: 3.00

Comments about grade suggestion: Tosi sujuva, mutta ei ihan näin hyvä.

On the bottom right of this view the teacher can give feedback on the Digitala plugin to the address set by the admin. On the bottom left the teacher can suggest changes and add feedback to the automatic assessment.

Figure: Buttons for changing grades or giving feedback

Figure: Suggesting changes/adding feedback to automatic grades

Edit the evaluation report

Fluency	<input type="text" value="3.00"/>
Feedback on Fluency	<input type="text" value="I think you could have had a bit less pauses in your speech. Otherwise excellent!"/>

The most recent teacher suggestions will be shown on the student report page both for the teacher and the student.

Figure: Teacher comments on detailed student report

Esimerkki

Assignment Material

Assignment
Language: Finnish | Type: Freeform
Kerro koulumatkastasi.

Evaluation report - Includes some teacher feedback
Submitted: 24.04.2022 19:27:17

This feedback concerns only the speech sample you produced and it does not cover all aspects of your oral language skills. A machine produces your grades automatically. We have taught the machine with speech from other language learners together with other language-specific data.

There is no limit set for the number of attempts on this assignment.

▶ 0:00 / 0:06 ◀ 🔊 ⋮

A transcript of your speech sample
min koulumatka oli viis killo saa mä kuulin sitä aina polukun pyörelä

Analytic grading Proficiency level More information

Fluency

0 0.5 1.0 1.5 2.0 2.5 3.0 3.5 4.0

4/4

This measure reflects the speed, pauses, and hesitations in your speech. Based on the automatic grading, it seems that your speech is very fluent and no disturbing pauses, breaks, or hesitations occur.

Teacher's grade suggestion: 3.00

Comments about grade suggestion: I think you could have had a bit less pauses in your speech. Otherwise excellent!

Download database reports

In the overview of the student results, the teacher can download the database information of both the student attempts and the teacher suggestions and feedback in a CSV-form. They can also download all the students' recordings as a zipped folder of wav-files.

Figure: Downloading database reports

User results ⚙️

Student	Pronunciation	Time	Tries	Status	Timestamp	Evaluation report	Delete all
Admin User	4.00	00:04	4	Evaluated	26.04.2022 16.40:58	See report	Delete attempt
Essi Esimerkki	4.00	00:04	1	Evaluated	24.04.2022 19.30:17	See report	Delete attempt

[Export all attempts as CSV](#)
[Export all feedbacks for attempts as CSV](#)

The database information includes more detailed information received from the evaluation API such as fluency features or pronunciation features which constitute the score for fluency and pronunciation.

Student usage

A student can * test their microphone on the first view * see the assignment prompt and materials on the assignment view * record, listen and submit their speech performance on the assignment view * receive an automated evaluation of their performance on the evaluation view * see teacher's feedback about the automated evaluation * give feedback on the Digitala plugin

Testing microphone

On the first view the student can test if their microphone works. The browser may ask to give permissions to use the microphone. The student can record a speech snippet and try to playback the sound. If everything sounds right and the microphone icon shows a green circle behind it, the settings are fine for the assignment. If there's something to correct with the microphone permissions, the play button will prompt to check settings.

<https://user-images.githubusercontent.com/6292793/166822300-d0f5d656-5e74-4fb9-8ea1-b5108ce5bfa7.mp4>

Figure: Microphone testing view

Testing the mic is optional. The student can move to the next phase from navigation bar on the top or button on the bottom.

The assignment and materials

On the assignment page the student can see the assignment prompt on the left and additional materials on the right.

Figure: Freeform assignment view

1 Begin 2 Assignment 3 Evaluation

Assignment

Kerro uhanalaisista eläimistä.

Record your answer

There is no limit set for the number of attempts on this assignment.

00:00 / 02:00

Record ▶

Listen to your recording ◀

< Previous

Material

- Mitä uhanalaisia eläimiä tiedät?
- Miksi joistain eläimistä tulee uhanalaisia?
- Miten niitä voisi suojella?

If the assignment is a Readaloud type, then the text to be read is on the material box.

Figure: Readaloud assignment view

1 Begin 2 Assignment 3 Evaluation

Assignment

Lue oheinen teksti huolellisesti ääneen.

Record your answer

Number of attempts remaining: 2

00:00 / 01:00

Record ▶

Listen to your recording ◀

< Previous

Material

Tiikeri on suuri Panthera-sukuun kuuluva uhanalainen kissaeläinlaji, joka elää Itä- ja Kaakkois-Aasiassa, enimmäkseen trooppisissa sademetsissä. Tiikerin turkki on oranssinsävyinen ja siinä on tummia poikkijuovia. Tiikeri painaa yleensä noin 100–270 kilogrammaa ja sen säkäkorkeus on noin 100–110 senttimetriä. Tiikeri on jaettu kahteen alalajiin. Se on lihansyöjä, eikä sillä ole muita vihollisia kuin ihminen.

Bottom left there's a box for the recording. This box also shows if there's a time limit for the recording or submission limit to the assignment.

Recording and submitting speech

The student can record their answer to the assignment multiple times by clicking the start and stop buttons on the recording box. After stopping a submission button is shown.

https://user-images.githubusercontent.com/6292793/166822260-c2c4116b-d82c-41e0-afbc-093f985a711b.mp4

Figure: Submit answer

If the student chooses to submit, the Digitala will redirect to the report page and show a loading symbol and text during the automated assessment. The evaluation can take from seconds to minutes depending on the recording duration and other variables. On the page student can check if the evaluation is done, but if moving to other pages and returning when the evaluation is done, it will show automatically.

Figure: Evaluation in progress

At this point the student is free to move in the Moodle and come later to check if the evaluation is ready. When the evaluation is in a waiting status, the recording ability on the assignment page is also disabled.

Evaluation report of speech

After the automated evaluation a report of the speech performance can be shown on the third phase. This includes the recording and a transcript of the speech.

<https://user-images.githubusercontent.com/6292793/166822351-c6498be2-4a0a-4257-9cad-9ce13cd5c0e1.mp4>

Figure: Evaluation report

Evaluation report

Submitted: 24.04.2022 19.16:36

This feedback concerns only the speech sample you produced and it does not cover all aspects of your oral language skills. A machine produces your grades automatically. We have taught the machine with speech from other language learners together with other language-specific data.

There is no limit set for the number of attempts on this assignment.

A transcript of your speech sample

no yks uhan alainen eläin on ainakin toit tiikäritossa

Analytic grading

Proficiency level

More information

Fluency

This measure reflects the speed, pauses, and hesitations in your speech.

Based on the automatic grading, it seems that your speech is very fluent and no disturbing pauses, breaks, or hesitations occur.

Pronunciation

Above you can see that the machine transformed your speech into text. There you can check whether you pronounced all the words right. This measure reflects how well the machine understands your speech. The speech samples that the machine has heard before affect its ability to understand you.

The Readaloud type includes a transcript showing missing parts in orange underline and incorrect parts in skyblue.

Figure: Readaloud corrections

Charts show the student's score with an orange vertical line and the black dots on charts hold the descriptions of different grades.

Figure: Charts

Fluency

This measure reflects the speed, pauses, and hesitations in your speech.

4/4

Based on the automatic grading, it seems that your speech is very fluent and no disturbing pauses, breaks, or hesitations occur.

Teacher's grading suggestions

If a teacher has suggested changes to the automated evaluation, the title of the evaluation report will show as "Evaluation report - includes some teacher feedback".

Figure: Report with feedback 1

Evaluation report **includes some teacher feedback**

This feedback concerns only the speech sample you produced and it does not cover all aspects of your oral language skills. A machine produces your grades automatically. We have taught the machine with speech from other language learners together with other language-specific data.

Number of attempts remaining: 5

▶ 0:00 / 0:00 ———▶ 🔊 ⋮

Figure: Report with feedback 2

Fluency

This measure reflects the speed, pauses, and hesitations in your speech. Based on the automatic grading, it seems that your speech is very fluent and no disturbing pauses, breaks, or hesitations occur.

Teacher's grade suggestion: 3.00

Comments about grade suggestion: Tosi sujuva, mutta ei ihan näin hyvä.

The latest teacher grading suggestions and comments can be found on the bottom part of every grading box.

Give feedback on Digitala

On the bottom of the third page is a hovering link “Give feedback” which will pop up to a feedback box.

Figure: Feedback box

Pronunciation

0 0.5 1.0 1.5 2.0 2.5 3.0 3.5

3/4

Above you can see that the machine transformed your speech into text. There you can check whether pronounced all the words right. This measure reflects how well the machine understands your speech samples that the machine has heard before affect its ability to understand you. Based on the automatic seems that the machine understands you and there seems to be no major issues in your pronunciation.

Palautetta DigiTalan työkalusta

Kiitos, että kokeilit! Nyt voit antaa palautetta työkalusta. Kehitämme työkalua jatkuvasti saadun palautteen perusteella. Jos jokin ei toiminut, kerro millä laitteella ja selaimella käytit työkalua.

Voit myös ottaa yhteyttä sähköpostitse

Give feedback

The origin of this feedback site can be set by the administrator on the plugin settings. The pop up closes by clicking on it again.